

Data Access Policy

Longitudinal ALS Cohort

Authors

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Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Document history/approvals
v1.0.1	21.11.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Add DOI reference, fix text wording.
v1.0.0	20.11.2025	Manfredo Atzori	Review policy text.
v0.0.1	19.11.2025	Marcos Casado Barbero	Draft policy text.

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Policy Text

The **Longitudinal ALS Cohort** ⁵ contains highly sensitive, person-level clinical and genetic information on patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) and related motor neuron diseases, derived from routine healthcare at the University of Padua (UNIPD). The data include identifiable and potentially re-identifiable health information (e.g., dates, detailed clinical examinations, neuroimaging reports) and are therefore not made available through this Zenodo record.

The full dataset is stored and managed within UNIPD clinical and research infrastructures under the responsibility of the local clinical and research team. Any use of the data must remain compatible with the original purpose of collection and applicable approvals and must comply with relevant data protection legislation, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ⁶ the European Health Data Space Regulation (EHDS Regulation), ⁷ and the Italian Personal Data Protection Code (Italian Privacy Code), ⁸ as well as any other applicable national legislation and HEREDITARY governance.

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⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17671190>

⁶ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/2016-05-04>

⁷ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2025/327/oj>

⁸ <https://www.normattiva.it/eli/id/2003/07/29/003G0218/CONSOLIDATED>

At the present stage of the HEREDITARY project (GA 101137074),^{9,10} access to the underlying dataset is **not offered to the general public**. Access may be considered, on a case-by-case basis, for partners of the HEREDITARY consortium where the proposed use is scientifically justified, ethically and legally permissible, and covered by appropriate agreements between institutions. Interested HEREDITARY partners should **contact UNIPD's data controller at [manfredo.atzori\[at\]unipd.it](mailto:manfredo.atzori@unipd.it)**. Requests from organisations outside the HEREDITARY consortium are not currently foreseen.

⁹ <https://hereditary-project.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101137074>